

PARSEC DDOMP Workbook Checklist

August 2023

DDOMP¹ Introduction

The Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook (DDOMP) is to be used by the PARSEC team to (i) establish the policies the team will follow, (ii) document the operational procedures necessary to comply with those policies, and (iii) organize the planned activities necessary to manage PARSEC data, software, and other digital outputs. It is a working document.

This checklist is a summary of the team resources and the Data and Digital Output Management Schedule. As a PARSEC team member, you are responsible for supporting the activities defined in this checklist and further described in the full DDOMP. This is part of the Code of Conduct all members signed.

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PARSEC TEAM RESOURCES

For **material development and temporary storage**: [Google Drive](#) (main folder link)

For **team communications and information dissemination**: Email, WhatsApp

For **dataset storage during the project**:

- Amazon Web Services (AWS) – available through the Brazil team.
- Open Science Framework (OSF) - <https://osf.io/ak2bw/>

We have integrated these platforms to include the terms of use for the datasets we plan to use. Each of these platforms supports access/controls for our team members to protect the project space. OSF is integrated with our AWS, GitHub, and Google Drive.

For **datasets, images, and supporting object preservation** (except for software and training/workshop materials): Environmental Data Initiative

The [Environmental Data Initiative](#) (EDI, independently funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation) is a partner on the PARSEC project, and a preferred domain repository.

Details are posted: <https://environmentaldatainitiative.org/edi-data-policy-2/>

For **software development**: PARSEC Organization [GitHub](#)

For **software preservation**: Zenodo, link to our [PARSEC Community](#)

¹ Stall, Shelley, Specht, Alison, Corrêa, Pedro Luiz Pizzigatti, David, Romain, Edmunds, Rorie, Mabile, Laurence, Machicao, Jeaneth, Miyairi, Nobuko, Murayama, Yasuhiro, O'Brien, Margaret, Wyborn, Lesley, & Vellenich, Danton Ferreira. PARSEC Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3891426>

Zenodo is a well-known open-source general repository specializing in software preservation through [their partnership with GitHub](#). Once your software is in Zenodo, make corrections to the title, authors, and description to ensure a proper citation.

For **conference, training, and workshop materials preservation**: Zenodo, link to our [PARSEC Community](#).

For **credit and automated attribution**: PARSEC team members need to have active and up-to-date ORCID profiles that allow for automated updates from Crossref and DataCite.

For **reference management**: [Zotero](#) (contact sstall@agu.org for any permission issues)

Example of the **acknowledgement** to include in all digital outputs.

“This work is part of the 'Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Re-use through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas (PARSEC)' project with funding provided by the Belmont Forum through the National Science Foundation, NSF, Grant 1929464, (US), Agence Nationale de la Recherche, ANR (France), Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo, FAPESP (Brazil), and the Japan Science and Technology Agency, JST (Japan) with support from the synthesis centre CESAB of the French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity.”

PARSEC MEMBER DATA AND DIGITAL OUTPUT MANAGEMENT SCHEDULE

Once (in the lifetime of the researcher)

1. For your **ORCID profile**, activate the automatic updates from Crossref and DataCite. Reference [this page for instructions](#). To set up an ORCID profile, reference this [site](#).

Further information: [Checklist](#) and [recording/slides](#) about managing your digital presence and the importance of persistence identifiers.

Weekly

1. **Track Non Peer-Reviewed Digital Outputs** (to include Datasets, Software, Conferences, Posters, Presentations, training Materials, Workshop Materials, etc.)

All non peer-reviewed digital outputs published in Zenodo, or similar repository is to be listed in the tracking sheet managed in our Google Drive. A recent published version is here: [Non Peer-Reviewed Digital Output Tracking Tool](#)

Make sure you include acknowledgement of the Belmont Forum, and your country funder(s). Use the PARSEC logo.

2. **Update Dataset Log:** working log of datasets reviewed for use by the project.

Datasets reviewed by the PARSEC project team members are to be added to the log along with information about usefulness or concerns. The Dataset Log is managed in our Google Drive. A recent published version is here: [Dataset Log](#)

Note: published PARSEC datasets are included in Non Peer-Reviewed Digital Output above.

3. **Update Software Log:** working log to software reviewed by the project (to include Models, Notebooks, Workflow, etc.)

Software reviewed by the PARSEC project team members is to be added to the log along with information about usefulness or concerns. The Software Log is managed in our Google Drive. A recent published version is here: [Software Log](#)

Note: published PARSEC software is included in Non Peer-Reviewed Digital Output above.

Monthly

1. For any **planned peer-reviewed publications**, all supporting digital objects including datasets and software must be preserved and cited in your paper. Ensure all contributions to the digital objects (such as datasets) are accurately captured in the author/creator list.

Preservation tasks:

- Ensure all datasets and software used in your research are preserved and cited in the references section. Ensure these products are listed in the “Non Peer-Reviewed Digital Output Tracking Sheet” managed on the Google Drive.
- List your publication in the **Scholarly Publications** tracking sheet for the current reporting year. A recent published version is here: [Scholarly Publications](#)

Quarterly (every three months)

1. Update your ORCID profile and ensure that it is current and complete.

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